

STUDY OF VITAMIN D LEVELS AND URINE ALBUMIN TO CREATININE RATIO IN TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

VANSHIKA MALIK

3rd Year M.Sc. Student, Department of Biochemistry, School of Medical Sciences and Research and Sharda Hospital, Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India.

MANOJ KUMAR NANDKEOLIAR*

Professor, Department of Biochemistry, School of Medical Sciences and Research and Sharda Hospital, Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India.

*Corresponding Author Email: drmanoj55@gmail.com

SB SHARMA

Professor, Department of Biochemistry, School of Medical Sciences and Research and Sharda Hospital, Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India.

PREETI YADAV

Assistant Professor, Department of Biochemistry, School of Medical Sciences and Research and Sharda Hospital, Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India.

RENU CHANE

Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, School of Medical Sciences and Research and Sharda Hospital, Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India.

THURAYA ABDULSALAM A.A. ALAZAZI

PhD Scholar, Department of Biochemistry, School of Medical Sciences and Research and Sharda Hospital, Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India.

NIRUPMA GUPTA

Professor, Department of Anatomy, School of Medical Sciences and Research and Sharda Hospital, Sharda University, Greater Noida, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Abstract

Background: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is commonly linked to microvascular consequences such as Diabetic Nephropathy (DN). Vitamin D (VD) affects renal functions, insulin sensitivity and glucose metabolism in addition to regulation of calcium metabolism. The present study was carried out to find the relationship between serum VD levels and Urinary Albumin to Creatinine Ratio (UACR) in T2DM to study the early onset of renal disease in T2DM. **Aim & Objectives:** This study investigates the correlation between vitamin D levels and UACR in patients with T2DM. **Material & Methods:** A case-control study was conducted involving 90 subjects, comprising of 45 newly diagnosed T2DM patients and 45 age- and sex-matched healthy controls. Fasting Blood Glucose was estimated by GOD-POD method, Serum vitamin D levels by ELISA and UACR by Kit based dry chemistry method on fully automated Biochemistry analyzer. **Results:** Patients with type 2 diabetes had substantially lower levels of vitamin D and higher levels of glucose ($p < 0.0001$). The correlation between serum vitamin D levels (ng/mL) and Urine Albumin to Creatinine Ratio (UACR, mg/g) was found to be inverse relation but statistically insignificant with a correlation coefficient of $r = -0.152$ indicating that lower Vitamin D status is associated with increased urinary albumin excretion. **Conclusion:** In patients with T2DM lower serum VD levels are significantly associated with elevated UACR indicating a potential link between VD deficiency and the progression of DKD. Monitoring and correcting VD deficiency might offer a therapeutic avenue to mitigate albuminuria and delay the onset or progression of DKD.

Keywords: Vitamin D, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Urine Albumin to Creatinine Ratio, Diabetic Nephropathy.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus (DM) is a multifaceted metabolic condition that is complicated by abnormalities in insulin secretion or activity that lead to hyperglycemia. Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), which is defined by hyperglycemia brought on by abnormalities in insulin production or action, is a serious and rapidly worsening worldwide health concern. The primary cause of T2DM are insulin resistance or relative insulin insufficiency **(1)**. Microvascular problems, particularly Diabetic Nephropathy (DN), are often linked to this metabolic disease and significantly increase morbidity, death, and healthcare expenses globally. **(2)**

The rising health burden of T2DM has grown to be a significant global problem in recent decades. According to estimates, the prevalence of diabetes among adults aged 20 to 79 was 10.5% worldwide in 2021 (536.6 million), and it will increase to 12.2% (783.2 million) in 2045. The prevalence of type 2 diabetes is very high in India, where millions of people are afflicted. **(2,3,4)** About 102.6 million persons in India have diabetes, according to recent research in 2023, making it one of the nation with the highest prevalence of the disease. This number illustrates the significant public health concern that T2DM poses in India, since it accounts for around 11.4% of the adult population. **(5)**

One of the main cause of end-stage renal disease is Diabetic Kidney Disease (DKD) **(6)**. Urine albumin excretion, as measured by the Urine Albumin-to-Creatinine Ratio (UACR), is frequently monitored in order to diagnose DKD early. An elevated UACR is a precursor to renal impairment in people with type 2 diabetes. **(7)** VD may also affect insulin sensitivity, renal function, and glucose metabolism. **(8)** The pathophysiology and development of certain diabetes-related problems, including DKD, have therefore been linked to vitamin D insufficiency. **(9)**

People with diabetes, especially those with renal involvement, may have VD insufficiency due to a number of causes. The loss of Vitamin D Binding Protein (VDBP) in the urine due to proteinuria, a typical symptom of DKD, might lower the amount of VD in the blood. Furthermore, the transformation of inactive VD into its active form may be impacted by compromised renal function. **(10)** The relationship between serum VD levels and UACR in T2DM patients has been the subject of several investigations.

A possible function of VD in preventing kidney injury is suggested by certain data that show an inverse connection between lower VD levels and greater UACR. Nevertheless, the findings of other studies have been mixed, with some revealing weak correlations or non-linear associations. These disparities emphasize the necessity of further research to elucidate this relationship. **(11)**

The present study sheds light on the association between UACR and serum vitamin D levels in order to understand how VD status may contribute to the onset and course of DKD in this group. VD supplementation may be a possible treatment or prophylactic strategy for DKD in individuals with type 2 diabetes.

MATERIAL & METHODS

A case- control study was conducted in the Department of Biochemistry and Medicine at Sharda Hospital, Greater Noida after obtaining ethical clearance from Institutional Ethical Committee. A total of 90 participants were recruited and divided into two groups, 45 diagnosed T2DM patients based on the American Diabetes Association (ADA) 2022 criteria and 45 age- and sex-matched healthy controls.

Inclusion Criteria were subjects in the age group of 30 to 60 years, confirmed diagnosis of T2DM and no intake of vitamin D supplements for at least four weeks before enrolment. **Exclusion criteria** was the presence of chronic illnesses such as liver or renal disease, pregnancy, long-term steroid use, cancer and other comorbidities associated with T2DM.

Following written informed consent, Fasting Blood Glucose samples were collected from all participants and estimated by using the Glucose Oxidase- Peroxidase (GOD-POD) method. Serum vitamin D levels were measured by using an ELISA and UACR by Kit based method.

RESULTS

Fasting Blood Glucose levels in healthy controls (92.18 ± 11.74 mg/dl) were significantly lower compared to T2DM cases (268 ± 53.09 mg/dl), with a highly significant difference ($p < 0.0001$) Table-1

Table 1: Fasting Blood Glucose levels in Healthy Controls and Type 2 Diabetic Patients

Fasting blood glucose (mg/dl)	Controls(n=45)	Cases(n=45)	P value
Mean \pm SD	92.18 \pm 11.74	268 \pm 53.09	<.0001
Range	73-110	176-416	

Serum Vitamin D levels in healthy controls (32.02 ± 11.34 ng/ml) were significantly higher compared to T2DM cases (10.47 ± 2.32 ng/ml), with a highly significant difference ($p < 0.0001$) Table 2

Table 2: Serum Vitamin D levels in Healthy Controls and Type 2 Diabetic Patients

Vitamin D (ng/ml)	Controls(n=45)	Cases(n=45)	P value
Deficient {<20 ng/ml}	9 (20%)	45 (100%)	<.0001
Insufficient {20-30 ng/ml}	8 (17.78%)	0 (0%)	
Sufficient {>30 ng/ml}	28 (62.22%)	0 (0%)	
Mean \pm SD	32.02 \pm 11.34	10.47 \pm 2.32	<.0001
Median (25th-75th percentile)	36.07 (22.2-41.02)	10.66 (8.99-12.03)	
Range	11.06-46.7	6.02-15.09	

UACR levels in healthy controls (30.65 ± 29.92 mg/g) were significantly lower compared to T2DM cases (289.88 ± 58.73 mg/g), with a highly significant difference ($p < 0.0001$) Table-3

Table 3: UACR in Healthy Controls and Type 2 Diabetic Patients

UACR (mg/g)	Controls(n=45)	Cases(n=45)	P value
Mean \pm SD	30.65 ± 29.92	289.88 ± 58.73	<.0001
Range	2.62-164.6	186.6-424.5	

The correlation between serum vitamin D levels (ng/ml) and Urine Albumin to Creatinine Ratio (UACR, mg/g) was found to be inverse relation but statistically insignificant with a correlation coefficient of $r = -0.152$ indicating that lower Vitamin D status is associated with increased urinary albumin excretion Table 4 & Figure 4.

Table 4: Correlation of vitamin D (ng/ml) with UACR (mg/g)

Variables	UACR (mg/g)
Vitamin D (ng/ml)	
Correlation coefficient	-0.152
P value	0.318

Figure 4: Correlation of vitamin D (ng/mL) with UACR (mg/g)

Significant moderately positive correlation was seen between fasting blood sugar (mg/dl) with UACR (mg/g) with correlation coefficient of 0.403. (Table 5 & Figure 5)

Table 5: Correlation between FBS with UACR

Variables	UACR (mg/g)
Fasting blood sugar (mg/dl)	
Correlation coefficient	0.403
P value	0.006

Figure 5: Correlation of fasting blood sugar (mg/dl) with UACR (mg/g)

DISCUSSION

The present case-control study aimed to study the relationship between VD levels and the levels of UACR in the patients of Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), the findings revealed a significantly lower level of vitamin D in T2DM patients compared to healthy controls. Additionally, UACR was markedly elevated in the Diabetic group, indicating a higher prevalence of albuminuria, a marker of early Diabetic Nephropathy.

Vitamin D deficiency has been increasingly recognized as a contributing factor in the progression of various chronic diseases, including diabetes and its complications. In this study, UACR (mg/g) and fasting blood glucose (mg/dl) showed a moderately positive correlation with UACR that was statistically insignificant, suggesting that greater albumin excretion was linked to higher fasting glucose levels. According to a study by Jianling Song, et.al. in 2024 there is a strong correlation between higher UACR and higher FBG levels. (12)

The correlation between serum vitamin D levels (ng/ml) and Urine Albumin to Creatinine Ratio (UACR, mg/g) was found to be inverse relation but statistically insignificant with a correlation coefficient of $r = -0.152$ indicating that lower Vitamin D status is associated with increased urinary albumin excretion.

These findings align with a study by Seyed Alireza Zomorodian, et. al. in 2022 that in individuals with type 2 diabetes, albuminuria was negatively correlated with serum 25-hydroxyvitamin D [25(OH)D] levels. In particular, higher Urine Albumin-to-Creatinine Ratio (UACR) values, which indicate more severe albuminuria, were associated with lower 25(OH)D levels. Patients with macroalbuminuria (UACR ≥ 300 mg/g) had a significantly greater frequency of vitamin D insufficiency than those with microalbuminuria or normo-albuminuria.

It was determined that the ideal cut-off point for predicting macroalbuminuria was a 25(OH)D serum level ≤ 21 ng/ml. Although they stress the need for more extensive prospective studies to prove a direct link between vitamin D levels and albuminuria, the authors speculate that treating vitamin D deficiency may decrease macroalbuminuria and related cardiovascular events in diabetes individuals. **(13)**

Hong SH et al. conducted another investigation in 2021 showed an independent correlation between high UACR, a sign of diabetic nephropathy, and 25(OH)D deficit [25(OH)D < 20 ng/ml]. **(14)** Furthermore, studies have shown that administration of VD in patients with type 2 diabetes with chronic kidney disease reduces albuminuria, which suggests that vitamin D may play a part in the development of diabetic nephropathy.

This is supported by the increased frequency of VD deficiency in patients with microalbuminuria. These findings highlight the importance of maintaining appropriate VD status monitoring in T2DM patients which may help to prevent the establishment of diabetic nephropathy.

From a clinical perspective, our findings suggest that routine screening of VD levels in patients with T2DM may be beneficial, particularly in those at risk for nephropathy. Early detection and correction of VD deficiency could potentially serve as a low-cost and non-invasive intervention to delay or prevent the onset of renal complications in diabetes. These results highlight vitamin D's possible involvement in the pathogenesis of diabetic nephropathy and warrant further research into its potential therapeutic uses.

CONCLUSION

In patients with T2DM lower serum VD levels are significantly associated with elevated UACR indicating a potential link between VD deficiency and the progression of Diabetic Nephropathy. These findings suggest that VD status may play a role in renal functions and could serve as a modifiable risk factor for early kidney damage in T2DM. Monitoring and correcting VD deficiency might offer a therapeutic avenue to mitigate albuminuria and delay the onset or progression of DN.

In conclusion, the interplay between VD and albuminuria in T2DM patients sheds light on a modifiable risk factor for Diabetic Nephropathy. Further research is warranted to assess the therapeutic benefits of VD supplementation in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus in order to prevent the progression of renal damage

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